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Full book

Mays C, Laborie L, Griset P (eds) (2022) [Inventing a shared science diplomacy for Europe: Interdisciplinary case studies to think with history](#). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590096>

Introductions

Bertelsen, Rasmus Gjedssø (2022) [Debating across history, theory and strategy for European science diplomacy](#). In Mays C, Laborie L, Griset P (eds) *Inventing a shared science diplomacy for Europe: Interdisciplinary case studies to think with history*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6639762>

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Case studies

Science diplomats

Diogo, Maria Paula, Urze, Paula & Simões, Ana (2022) [Enacting soft power: Cartoons, technoscience diplomacy and the 1890 British Ultimatum to Portugal](#). In Mays C, Laborie L, Griset P (eds) *Inventing a shared science diplomacy for Europe: Interdisciplinary case studies to think with history*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6600855>

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Laborie, Léonard (2022) [Scientists attached to diplomacy: French and German explorers calling for diplomatic accreditation before the First World War](#). In Mays C, Laborie L, Griset P (eds) Inventing a shared science diplomacy for Europe: Interdisciplinary case studies to think with history. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6600906>

Ruffini, Pierre-Bruno (2022) [Science diplomacy in the field: An immersion in the life of science counselors of the European Union](#). In Mays C, Laborie L, Griset P (eds) Inventing a shared science diplomacy for Europe: Interdisciplinary case studies to think with history. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6600928>

Simões, Ana & Diogo, Maria Paula (2022) [Science diplomacy in the Republic of Letters: The naturalist Abbé Correia da Serra](#). In Mays C, Laborie L, Griset P (eds) Inventing a shared science diplomacy for Europe: Interdisciplinary case studies to think with history. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6600931>

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Heritage

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Fägersten, Björn (2022) [Leveraging Science Diplomacy in an Era of Geo-Economic Rivalry: Towards a European strategy](#). Strategy report. Stockholm: The Swedish Institute of International Affairs.

InsSciDE (2019) [Building an interdisciplinary European science diplomacy](#). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6570336>.

InsSciDE (2022) [Framing EU Health Diplomacy with a global and systemic worldview](#). Issue paper 2 prepared by Daniella Palmberg.

InsSciDE (2022) [Europe meets the world on the ocean: A case for ocean science diplomacy](#). Issue paper 3 prepared by Daniella Palmberg.

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